

Recent Advancement in Drug Development for Intranasal Drug Delivery System

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ABSTRACT

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A growing number of researchers are interested in exploring the possibility of nasal medication delivery as an alternate route of administration for vaccines and biomolecules like proteins, peptides, and non-peptide pills. As a legitimate method of treatment, intranasal therapy has gained acceptance within the ayurvedic medical system. Medications that undergo substantial degradation in the gastrointestinal tract or are metabolised by the first pass effect in the liver when taken orally are often more stable when administered via the nasal route. A long-term alternative to parenteral therapy, the nasal route has its uses in both acute and chronic settings. The nasal mucosa is very permeable and has a high vascularization rate, which allows for quick absorption and action beginning. Since the medication enters the systemic circulation straight from the nasal route, it is not only useful for local treatments but also for systemic therapy. When administering tiny molecules via the nasal route, absorption is good; when administering large molecules, absorption promoters can improve absorption even further. This article provides a high-level summary of intranasal medication administration, covering topics such as methods to increase bioavailability and elements influencing nasal absorption.

Graphical Abstract:

1. Introduction

1.1 Nasal Drug delivery system

Medications intended for local effects were first applied topically, and this practice evolved into nasal medication delivery. The Ayurvedic medical system of India recognises nasal therapy, also known as "Nasya karma," as a valid method of treatment. One potential systemic delivery alternative to more traditional methods was the nasal route, which was introduced in the early 1980s. Quick absorption of chemicals into the systemic circulation, bypassing the hepatic first pass clearance, is provided by the nasal route, which is easily accessible, easy, and dependable due to its highly vascularized epithelium and porous endothelium membrane. Less side effects, faster onset of pharmacological action, reduced dosage, and faster attainment of therapeutic blood levels are all possible with intranasal medication delivery. The nasal cavity's low metabolic environment may be able to circumvent the oral route's limitations and provide the same effect as intravenous treatment. Furthermore, nasal administration provides noninvasiveness, self-administration, patient comfort, and patient compliance, which are challenges in intravenous drug therapy, while also minimising the lag time linked with oral drug delivery. The pharmacokinetic profiles of lipophilic drugs absorbed from the nasal cavity are often the same as those of intravenous injections, and their bioavailability is close to 100%. In contrast, absorption enhancers can boost the absorption of hydrophilic drugs. The nasal cavity is being used for

the delivery of a wide variety of drugs, from tiny molecules to massive macromolecules, such as hormones, vaccinations, peptide/protein therapies, and more. One promising strategy for delivering active chemicals to the central nervous system (CNS) directly into the BioPhase is nasal administration, which avoids the blood-brain barrier (BBB). Vaccine administration has also been contemplated. Some peptides that have been effectively delivered nasally include busserelin, desmopressin, calcitonin, insulin, growth hormone, luteinizing hormone releasing hormone, and adreno-corticotrophic hormone. Antihypertensives (nifedipine, nitroglycerine, propranolol, hydralazine, etc.), steroids (corticosteroids, estradiol, progesterone, testosterone, etc.), analgesics (buprenorphine), antibiotics, and antivirals all have significant systemic effects when given through the nose. Several methods have been investigated for the administration of drugs through the nose, including nasal pumps, gels, microemulsions, suspensions, powders, and thermoreversible mucoadhesive gels. Drug distribution through the nasal route has been a growing area of interest for pharmaceutical researchers and clinicians over the last several decades [1].

Since the nasal mucosa is less diluted by gastrointestinal contents, has a neutral pH, and is permeable to more compounds than the gastrointestinal tract (due to the absence of pancreatic and gastric enzymatic activity), it has been proposed as a possible route of administration to achieve faster

and higher levels of drug absorption. The systemic bioavailability of numerous medications has been demonstrated to be higher when administered nasally rather than orally in recent years. In Ayurvedic Indian medicine, nasal therapy—also known as "NASAYA KARMA"—is a recognised method of treatment. Traditional nasal medicine delivery methods have been revitalised after thousands of years of use. Because proteins and peptides do not have minimal oral bioavailability and are effective at low doses, this delivery strategy is ideal for these medications. The quick removal of peptides and proteins from the nasal cavity at the hands of the mucociliary clearance process is one explanation for the poor level of absorption when using this route. Since the nasal route avoids the liver's first pass elimination that occurs with oral administration, it's convenient for self-medication and easy to get. Drug distribution through the nasal route has been a growing area of interest for pharmaceutical researchers and medical professionals over the last several decades. All sorts of drug candidates have been tested on animals, from tiny metal ions to massive macromolecular proteins. A more thorough absorption of several steroids and hormones has been shown when administered nasally. Both the local effects and the systemic medicine administration via the nasal route may have some useful applications in this regard. Nostril administration of topical and systemic medications has a long history. Congestion, rhinitis, sinusitis, and associated allergy or chronic disorders can be treated with a range of topical drugs, including corticoids, antihistamines, anti-cholinergics, and vasoconstrictors. Systemic medication administration by the nose has been the primary focus of the growing number of studies examining this route in recent years. The current market offers only a limited selection of nasal delivery systems that have been tested in clinical trials. These include aqueous nasal sprays, nasal gel pumps, pressurised MDIs, dry powder inhalers, and multiple-or single-dose nasal drops. Patients suffering from migraines, nocturnal enuresis, osteoporosis, severe pain, nicotine addiction, and vitamin B12 insufficiency are among those now receiving treatment through intranasal administration. Therapy for cancer, epilepsy, rheumatoid arthritis, insulin-dependent diabetes, and anti-emetics are among the other therapeutic areas being studied or that may benefit from nasal

administration. Here we take a quick look at the pros and cons of nasal drug delivery systems, as well as the anatomy of the nasal cavity, the process of nasal absorption, the obstacles to nasal absorption, ways to overcome these obstacles, problems with nasal drug delivery formulation, and some examples of their use [2] (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Olfactory pathway for nose to brain drug delivery

2. Drug development and advancement

The fast ageing of populations is a major factor in the rising expense of healthcare, and neurological illnesses are on the rise as a result. The blood-brain barrier has made the discovery of neuroprotective medicines quite challenging thus far. Administering medications intranasally to noninvasively breach the blood-brain barrier is one innovative way to tackle this difficulty. Medications can be delivered to the brain directly from the nasal cavity through the intranasal route, which follows the olfactory and trigeminal nerves. In order to guide future studies, this review aims to explain this mechanism in depth. Two routes, one intracellular and one extracellular, make up the intranasal route. The process starts with the olfactory sensory cells endocytosing the drug, which is then transported to their synaptic clefts in the olfactory bulb by axonal transport. Olfactory neurones distribute the medication to different brain regions by repeating this transsynaptic procedure. The extracellular route for drug transport involves navigating the nasal epithelium, the paracellular space, the perineural space, and finally the subarachnoid space of the brain. Research in this area is becoming increasingly fascinating as more and more treatments hit the market, thanks to the

increasing amount of evidence and trials conducted in both rodent and human models [3].

New and improved techniques of administering medications are constantly being sought after. One efficient and non-invasive administration route is the nasal cavity. Its applications include vaccination administration and local and systemic targeting, as well as brain targeting. Despite the abundance of intranasal medicines on the market, most of them are reserved for local delivery, leaving few options for other target populations. Nasal delivery has gained traction as a potential strategy for medication delivery due to the fast expansion of nanotechnology's use in this field [4].

3. Profile of an ideal drug Candidate for nasal drug delivery

The formulation should have an appropriate water solubility to deliver the required dosage in a 25-150 ml volume administered nasally. Appropriate nasal absorption characteristics. The medicine does not irritate the nose (Table 1). The quick beginning of action is one good therapeutic reason for nasal dose forms. Dosage on the low side. In most cases, less than 25 mg each dosage. No harmful byproducts in the nose. There is no unpleasant smell or perfume linked to the medicine. Appropriate stability properties [5].

Table 1 The Following are the ideal drug candidate for nasal drug delivery

S. No	Name of the Drug	Categories	Disease or Disorder	Target Site	References
1	Sumatriptan	Sumatriptan belongs to the category of drugs known as triptans.	Sumatriptan is used to treat migraines and cluster headaches.	Sumatriptan targets serotonin (5-HT1B/1D) receptors in the brain.	[6]
2	Calcitonin	Calcitonin is a hormone that belongs to the category of peptide hormones.	Calcitonin plays a role in regulating calcium levels in the body and is associated with conditions like medullary thyroid carcinoma when levels are abnormal.	Calcitonin primarily acts on the bones to inhibit calcium release.	[7]
3	Desmopressin	Desmopressin belongs to the therapeutic category of drugs known as vasopressin analogues.	Desmopressin is used to treat conditions like diabetes insipidus or nocturnal enuresis (bed-wetting).	Desmopressin primarily acts on the renal collecting ducts to enhance water reabsorption.	[8]
4	Naloxone	Naloxone is classified as an opioid antagonis	Naloxone is used to reverse opioid overdose by blocking opioid receptors.	The target site of naloxone is opioid receptors in the central nervous system	[9]
5	Oxytocin	Oxytocin belongs to the category of neuropeptides.	Oxytocin dysfunction can contribute to social cognition deficits and affect bonding behaviors.	Oxytocin primarily targets the uterus and mammary glands.	[10]
6	Fluticasone	Fluticasone belongs to the category of corticosteroid, specifically glucocorticoids.	Fluticasone is commonly used to treat inflammatory conditions of the airways, particularly asthma and allergic rhinitis (hay fever).	The target site of fluticasone is the glucocorticoid receptor.	[11]
7	Oxymetazoline	Oxymetazoline belongs to the category of topical nasal decongestants.	Oxymetazoline can cause rebound congestion if used for more than a few days due to its vasoconstrictive effects on nasal mucosa.	Oxymetazoline primarily targets alpha-adrenergic receptors in the nasal mucosa to reduce nasal congestion.	[12]

8	Budesonide	Budesonide belongs to the category of corticosteroid	Budesonide is primarily used to treat inflammatory conditions like asthma and Crohn's disease.	The target site of budesonide is primarily the lungs, where it exerts its anti-inflammatory effects.	[13]
9	Triamcinolone	Triamcinolone belongs to the category of corticosteroids.	Triamcinolone can lead to adverse effects such as osteoporosis, hypertension, and hyperglycemia.	The target site of triamcinolone is the glucocorticoid receptor.	[14]
10	Midazolam	Midazolam is categorized as a benzodiazepine.	Midazolam is commonly used to treat seizures, anxiety and to induce sedation before medical procedure or surgery.	Midazolam targets and binds to benzodiazepine receptors in the central nervous system.	[15]
11	Fentanyl	Fentanyl is a potent synthetic opioid categorized as a Schedule II controlled substance due to its high potential for abuse and dependence.	Fentanyl is a potent synthetic opioid primarily used for pain management but can lead to severe respiratory depression and overdose if misused.	Fentanyl primarily targets and binds to opioid receptors in the central nervous system.	[16]
12	Beclomethasone	Beclomethasone is a corticosteroid used to prevent and control symptoms of asthma and allergic rhinitis.	Beclomethasone is used primarily to treat inflammatory conditions such as asthma and allergic rhinitis.	The target site of beclomethasone in short is the glucocorticoid receptors.	[17]
13	Mometasone	Mometasone belongs to the category of corticosteroids.	Mometasone is commonly used to treat inflammatory skin conditions such as eczema (atopic dermatitis) and psoriasis.	Mometasone primarily targets glucocorticoid receptors to exert its anti-inflammatory effects.	[18]
14	Lidocaine	Lidocaine is classified as a local anesthetic.	The most common adverse reaction to lidocaine is an allergy, marked by dermatitis.	Lidocaine primarily acts on voltage-gated sodium channels in nerves, blocking the initiation and conduction of nerve impulses.	[19]
15	Ketamine	Ketamine is categorized as a dissociative anesthetic.	Ketamine can induce dissociation, hallucinations, and, in some cases, dependency.	Ketamine primarily targets the NMDA receptors in the brain	[20]
16	Dihydroergotamine	Dihydroergotamine belongs to the pharmacological category of ergot alkaloids.	Dihydroergotamine is primarily used to treat migraines and cluster headaches. For the use of dihydroergotamine in treating migraines and cluster headaches.	The primary target site of dihydroergotamine is the serotonin (5-HT) receptors, particularly the 5-HT1B and 5-HT1D subtypes.	[21]
17	Granisetron	Granisetron belongs to the category of medications known as selective 5-HT3 receptor antagonists.	Granisetron is generally safe but may cause side effects like headache, constipation, or, rarely, serotonin syndrome.	Granisetron primarily targets and blocks the serotonin 5-HT3.	[22]
18	Dexamethasone	Dexamethasone belongs to the category	Dexamethasone is used to treat inflammatory	Dexamethasone primarily targets	[23]

		of drugs known as corticosteroids.	conditions, allergic disorders, and certain types of cancer.	glucocorticoid receptors in cells.	
19	Estradiol	Estradiol belongs to the category of hormones known as estrogens.	Elevated estradiol levels can indicate conditions like estrogen-producing tumors or ovarian dysfunction.	The target site of estradiol is estrogen receptors in the cells.	[24]
20	Azelastine	Azelastine belongs to the category of medication known as antihistamines.	Azelastine is primarily used to treat allergic rhinitis and related symptoms.	Azelastine primarily targets histamine H1 receptors.	[25]
21	Testosterone	Testosterone belongs to the category of hormones known as androgens.	Testosterone deficiency can lead to hypogonadism.	The primary target site of testosterone is androgen receptors located within cells.	[26]
22	Lorazepam	Lorazepam belongs to the category of drugs known as benzodiazepines.	Lorazepam is commonly used to treat anxiety disorders, including generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) and panic disorder.	Lorazepam acts on the gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) receptors in the central nervous system.	[27]
23	Epinephrine	Epinephrine belongs to the category of drugs known as "catecholamines".	The disorder related to epinephrine is "anaphylaxis "	Epinephrine primarily targets adrenergic receptors.	[28]
24	Triptorelin	Triptorelin is a gonadotropin-releasing hormone.	Triptorelin is primarily used to treat conditions like prostate cancer, endometriosis, and central precocious puberty.	Triptorelin primarily targets the pituitary gland.	[29]
25	Vasopressin	Vasopressin belongs to the category of hormones known as "peptide hormones".	Diabetes Insipidus (DI), a condition characterized by excessive thirst and urination, is related to vasopressin dysfunction or deficiency.	The target site of vasopressin (also known as antidiuretic hormone or ADH) is the kidneys.	[30]
26	Nicotine	Nicotine falls into the category of alkaloids.	Nicotine addiction.	Nicotine primarily targets and binds to Nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs) in the nervous system.	[31]
28	Metoclopramide	Metoclopramide is a medication classified as a prokinetic agent and antiemetic.	Metoclopramide can be associated with a side effects called Tardive Dyskinesia, which involves involuntary movements, often in the face and body.	Metoclopramide primarily acts on dopamine receptors in the gastrointestinal tract and central nervous system.	[32]
29	Ondansetron	Ondansetron belongs to the category of drugs known as serotonin 5-HT3 receptors antagonists.	Ondansetron is primarily used to prevent nausea and vomiting caused by chemotherapy, radiation therapy, or surgery.	Ondansetron primarily targets serotonin (5-HT3) receptors.	[33]
30	Ketorolac	Ketorolac belongs to the category of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs).	Ketorolac can cause gastrointestinal ulcers and bleeding, particularly with prolonged use.	Ketorolac primarily inhibits the enzyme cyclooxygenase (COX), thereby reducing prostaglandin synthesis.	[34]

				[34]	
31	Gentamicin	Gentamicin belongs to the category of antibiotics known as aminoglycosides.	Gentamicin: antibiotic associated with nephrotoxicity and ototoxicity.	Gentamicin targets bacterial ribosomes, specifically binding to the 30S subunit, thereby inhibiting protein synthesis.	[35]
32	Tobramycin	Tobramycin belongs to the category of antibiotics known as aminoglycosides.	Tobramycin is an antibiotic used to treat bacterial infections, particularly those affecting the lungs (e.g., cystic fibrosis-related infections).	The target site of tobramycin is bacterial ribosomes.	[36]
34	Sildenafil	Sildenafil belongs to the category of drugs known as PDE5 inhibitors.	Sildenafil is primarily used to treat erectile dysfunction (ED), which is a common disorder affecting male sexual function.	Sildenafil targets and inhibits the enzyme phosphodiesterase type 5 (PDE5) in the corpus cavernosum of the penis.	[37]
35	Butorphanol [38]	Butorphanol is categorized as a synthetic opioid analgesic.	Butorphanol is primarily used to treat pain and, in some cases, migraine headaches.	The primary target site of butorphanol is the Mu-opioid receptors in the central nervous system.	[38]
37	Lactitol	Lactitol belongs to the category of sugar alcohols or polyols.	Lactitol, a sugar alcohol used as a laxative, may cause gastrointestinal discomfort and bloating in some individuals.	The target site of lactitol is the colon, where it is metabolized by colonic bacteria.	[39]
39	Pseudoephedrine	Pseudoephedrine is classified as a decongestant.	Pseudoephedrine is commonly associated with potential misuse due to its use in producing illegal drugs like methamphetamine.	Pseudoephedrine primarily targets α -adrenergic receptors in the respiratory mucosa.	[40]
40	Levonorgestrel	Levonorgestrel belongs to the category of progestins (synthetic progestogens).	Levonorgestrel can cause irregular menstrual bleeding as a common side effect.	Levonorgestrel primarily acts as a progestin by binding to progesterone receptors.	[41]
41	Teriparatide	Teriparatide belongs to the category of drugs known as parathyroid hormone analogs.	Teriparatide is used to treat osteoporosis by stimulating bone formation.	Teriparatide primarily targets bone tissue to stimulate bone formation.	[42]
42	Scopolamine	Scopolamine belongs to the category of anticholinergic drugs.	Scopolamine is commonly used to treat motion sickness and nausea.	The target site of scopolamine is the central nervous system, specifically the brain.	[43]
43	Naltrexone	Naltrexone is categorized as an opioid antagonist.	Naltrexone is used to treat alcohol and opioid dependence by blocking opioid receptors, reducing cravings.	Naltrexone primarily acts as a competitive antagonist at opioid receptors.	[44]
44	Ropinirole	Ropinirole is categorized as a dopamine agonist.	Ropinirole is primarily used to treat Parkinson's disease and restless legs syndrome (RLS).	The target site of ropinirole is primarily dopamine receptors in the brain specifically the dopamine D2 and D3 receptors.	[45]

45	Montelukast	Montelukast belongs to the category of leukotriene receptor antagonists used for treating asthma and allergic rhinitis.	Montelukast may cause neuropsychiatric events such as agitation, aggression, and hallucinations in some patients.	Montelukast targets the cysteinyl leukotriene receptor to exert its pharmacological effects.	[46]
46	Apomorphine	Apomorphine is categorized as a dopamine agonist.	Apomorphine is primarily used in the treatment of Parkinson's disease.	Apomorphine acts on dopamine receptors in the brain, particularly targeting dopamine D2 receptors.	[47]
47	Clotrimazole	Clotrimazole belongs to the category of antifungal medication.	Clotrimazole is used to treat fungal infection, including athlete's foot, ringworm, and yeast infections like vaginal Candidiasis.	Clotrimazole targets fungal cell membranes by inhibiting ergosterol synthesis.	[48]
48	Antiemetics	Antiemetics belong to the category of drugs used to prevent or treat nausea and vomiting.	The abbreviation for "Disease or Disorder of antiemetics" would typically be "N/V ; standing for" nausea and vomiting".	The target site of antiemetics is typically the " CTZ", which stand for the chemoreceptor trigger zone in the brain.	[49]
49	Heparin	Heparin belongs to the category of anticoagulant medication.	The most common disorder associated with heparin use is heparin-induced thrombocytopenia (HIT).	The target site of heparin is antithrombin III (ATIII).	[50]
50	Salbutamol	Salbutamol belongs to the category of medication known as bronchodilators.	Sulbutamol is primarily used to treat asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD).	The target site of sulbutamol (also known as albuterol) is the beta-2 adrenergic receptors in the lungs.	[51]
51	Ipratropium	Ipratropium belongs to the family of medicines known as bronchodilators.	Ipratropium is primarily used in medicines to treat COPD.	Ipratropium primarily targets and acts on muscarinic receptors in the airways to produce bronchodilation.	[52]
52	Buserelin	Gonadotropin - releasing hormone (GnRH) analogue.	Endometriosis	Pituitary gland	[53]
53	Loratadine	Antihistamine	Allergies	Histamine receptors	[54]
54	Zanamivir	Antiviral	Influenza	Neuraminidase	[55]
55	Syntocinon	Oxytocic	Hypotension	Uterus	[56]
56	Rivastigmine	Rivastigmine belongs to the medication class known as cholinesterase inhibitors.	Rivastigmine is primarily used for Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease dementia.	Peripheral tissues	[57]
57	Cyclosporine	Cyclosporine is categorized as an immunosuppressant medication.	Renal toxicity	The target site of cyclosporine is the cyclophilin protein within cells.	[58]
58	Levodopa	The categorized of Levodopa is a dopamine precursor.	Levodopa is primarily used to treat Parkinson's disease. However,	The target site of Levodopa is the brain.	[59]

			levodopa-induced dyskinesias can sometimes be a side effect.		
59	Olanzapine	Olanzapine is classified as an atypical antipsychotic medication.	Hyperglycemia	Olanzapine primarily targets dopamine and serotonin receptors in the brain.	[60]
60	Clonidine	Clonidine belongs to the category of medication known as centrally acting alpha-agonists.	Clonidine is a medication primarily used to treat high blood pressure (Hypertension).	The target site of clonidine is the alpha 2 - adrenergic receptors in the central nervous system.	[61]
61	Olopatadine	Olopatadine is primarily classified as an antihistamine and mast cell stabilizer.	Olopatadine is primarily used to treat allergic conjunctivitis.	Olopatadine's target site is the histamine H1 receptor.	[62]
62	Rizatriptan	Rizatriptan belongs to a class of medications known as "triptans," which are used to treat migraine headaches.	Rizatriptan is primarily used for migraine headaches.	The target site of rizatriptan is the serotonin (5-HT1B/1D) receptor.	[63]
63	Desloratadine	Desloratadine is classified as a non-sedating antihistamine.	Desloratadine is commonly used to treat allergic conditions such as allergic rhinitis (hay fever).	Desloratadine targets histamine H1 receptors.	[64]
64	Tacrine	Tacrine belongs to the category of acetylcholinesterase inhibitors.	Hepatotoxicity	The target site of tacrine is acetylcholinesterase (AChE).	[65]
65	Nafarelin	Nafarelin is categorized as a gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) agonist.	The medication you're referring to is likely "leuprolide" or "nafarelin." This is a common medication used in hormone treatment therapy.	Nafarelin is a GnRH agonist, or an agonist of the GnRH receptor, the biological target of GnRH	[66]
66	Cyclobenzaparine	Cyclobenzaprine is categorized as a muscle relaxant.	Cyclobenzaprine is typically used to treat muscle spasms and related conditions, not a specific disease or disorder.	Cyclobenzaprine primarily targets the central nervous system, specifically acting on the brainstem, which helps to relieve muscle spasms.	[67]
67	Desogestrel	Desogestrel belongs to the category of progestins, which are synthetic forms of the hormone progesterone.	Desogestrel is associated with an increased risk of venous thromboembolism (VTE).	Desogestrel primarily targets the progesterone receptors in the reproductive system.	[68]
68	Selegiline	Selegiline is primarily categorized as a selective monoamine oxidase inhibitor (MAOI).	Selegiline is primarily used in the treatment of Parkinson's disease.	Selegiline primarily targets and inhibits monoamine oxidase type B (MAO-B) enzymes in the brain.	[69]
69	Zolpidem	Zolpidem belongs to the category of medications known as sedative-hypnotics or sleep aids.	One potential disorder associated with zolpidem is dependency or addiction.	Zolpidem targets the benzodiazepine site on the GABA-A receptor.	[70]
70	Tretinoin	Tretinoin belongs to the category of	Tretinoin-induced dermatitis	Tretinoin primarily acts on nuclear	[71]

		retinoids, specifically a derivative of vitamin A used primarily for dermatological purposes.		retinoic acid receptors (RARs) within skin cells.	
71	Cyclopentolate	Cyclopentolate is a muscarinic antagonist used as a mydriatic and cycloplegic agent in ophthalmology.	Cyclopentolate-induced cycloplegia, a temporary paralysis of the ciliary muscle in the eye, used in ophthalmic examinations.	Cyclopentolate targets muscarinic receptors in the eye, causing pupil dilation and paralysis of accommodation.	[72]
72	Cocaine hydrochloride	Cocaine is classified as a stimulant drug.	Cocaine Use Disorder (CUD)	Cocaine primarily targets and inhibits the reuptake of dopamine at neuronal synapses in the brain.	[73]
73	Cyanocobalamin	Cyanocobalamin belongs to the category of compounds known as cobalamins, which are a type of vitamin B12.	Cyanocobalamin deficiency can lead to pernicious anemia.	Cyanocobalamin primarily targets the vitamin B12 receptors in the body.	[74]
74	Lisinopril	Lisinopril belongs to the category of medications known as angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors.	Angioedema	Lisinopril primarily targets the angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) in the body.	[75]
75	Riluzole	Riluzole is categorized as a neuroprotective agent used in the treatment of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS).	Riluzole is primarily used to treat amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), a neurodegenerative disorder.	Riluzole's target site is the inhibition of glutamate release.	[76]
76	Nalbuphine	Nalbuphine is classified as a synthetic opioid analgesic, specifically a mixed agonist-antagonist.	Nalbuphine can induce respiratory depression at higher doses, particularly in susceptible individuals.	Nalbuphine acts as a κ -opioid receptor agonist and a μ -opioid receptor antagonist.	[77]
77	Salmeterol	Salmeterol is classified as a long-acting beta-agonist (LABA).	Salmeterol has been associated with an increased risk of asthma-related deaths.	Salmeterol targets and activates β_2 -adrenergic receptors on smooth muscle cells in the lungs.	[78]
78	Levobupivacaine	Levobupivacaine belongs to the category of local anesthetics.	Levobupivacaine toxicity can cause central nervous system.	Receptors	[79]
79	Lamotrigine	Lamotrigine is categorized as an anticonvulsant medication.	Stevens-Johnson Syndrome, a rare but serious skin reaction, can occur as a severe side effect of lamotrigine.	Lamotrigine primarily targets voltage-gated sodium channels in the central nervous system.	[80]
80	Donepezil	Donepezil belongs to the category of drugs known as acetylcholinesterase inhibitors.	Donepezil is a medication primarily used to treat Alzheimer's disease.	Donepezil targets and inhibits acetylcholinesterase in the brain .	[81]
81	Cromolyn	Cromolyn is categorized as a mast cell stabilizer.	Cromolyn is used to treat asthma and allergic rhinitis by inhibiting mast cell degranulation.	Cromolyn targets mast cells to inhibit the release of histamine and other inflammatory mediators.	[82]

82	Methimazole	Methimazole belongs to the category of medications known as antithyroid agents.	Methimazole is used primarily for the treatment of hyperthyroidism, including Graves' disease.	Methimazole targets the thyroid gland to reduce the production of thyroid hormones, specifically by inhibiting the enzyme hydroperoxides.	[83]
83	Tramadol	Tramadol is classified as a synthetic opioid analgesic used to treat moderate to severe pain.	Risk of respiratory depression and dependence.	Tramadol primarily targets the mu-opioid receptors in the central nervous system.	[84]
84	Misoprostol	Misoprostol is categorized as a synthetic prostaglandin E1 analog.	Abortion	Misoprostol primarily targets and binds to prostaglandin receptors, particularly EP2, EP3, and EP4 receptors.	[85]
85	Desvenlafaxine	Desvenlafaxine is classified as a serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor (SNRI).	Desvenlafaxine is a medication primarily used to treat major depressive disorder.	Desvenlafaxine primarily targets and inhibits the reuptake of serotonin and norepinephrine in the brain.	[86]
86	Methylphenidate	Methylphenidate is classified as a central nervous system (CNS) stimulant.	Disease or disorder treated with methylphenidate: Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD).	Methylphenidate primarily acts by blocking the reuptake of dopamine.	[87]
87	Cetirizine	Cetirizine belongs to the category of second-generation antihistamines used to treat allergies.	Drowsiness is a potential side effect of cetirizine.	Cetirizine primarily targets and antagonizes peripheral H1 histamine receptors.	[88]
88	Desipramine	Desipramine is a tricyclic antidepressant (TCA).	Desipramine is primarily used in the treatment of depression.	Desipramine primarily targets and inhibits the reuptake of norepinephrine at nerve terminals.	[89]
89	Ranitidine	Ranitidine belongs to the category of drugs known as H2 (histamine-2) receptor antagonists.	Ranitidine was a medication commonly used to reduce stomach acid production.	Ranitidine primarily targets the H2 receptors on gastric parietal cells.	[90]
90	Gemcitabine	Gemcitabine is classified as an antimetabolite chemotherapy agent used for cancer treatment.	Gemcitabine-induced thrombocytopenia.	Gemcitabine targets and inhibits DNA synthesis by interfering with the ribonucleotide reductase enzyme.	[91]
91	Pentamidine	Pentamidine belongs to the class of medications known as antiprotozoal agents.	Pentamidine is primarily used to treat pneumocystis pneumonia (PCP), a fungal infection often seen in immunocompromised individuals such as those with HIV/AIDS.	Pentamidine targets the kinetoplast DNA, specifically inhibiting the parasite's mitochondrial DNA replication.	[92]

92	Sufentanil	Sufentanil is a potent opioid analgesic commonly used for anesthesia and pain management in medical settings.	Sufentanil , a potent opioid , can lead to respiratory depression , addiction , and overdose when misused or abused.	Sufentanil primarily targets mu – opioid receptors in the central nervous system , producing potent analgesic effects .	[93]
93	Atropine	Atropine is classified as an anticholinergic medications .	Atropine can cause tachycardia , dry mouth , and blurred vision as side effects	Atropine acts primarily on muscarinic receptors in the parasympathetic nervous system .	[94]
94	Ciclesonide	Ciclesonide is a corticosteroid medication primarily used to treat asthma and allergic rhinitis .	Ciclesonide is commonly prescribed for asthma and allergic rhinitis .	Ciclesonide primarily targets the lungs and nasal passages to reduce inflammation.	[95]
95	Corticotropin	Corticotropin belongs to the category of peptide hormones .	Cushing’s syndrome results from excessive production of corticotropin (ACTH) by the pituitary gland .	The target site of corticotropin is the adrenal cortex .	[96]
96	Loxapine	Loxapine belongs to the class of medications known as typical antipsychotics.	Loxapine is primarily used to treat schizophrenia and other psychotic disorder .	Loxapine primarily acts on dopamine and serotonin receptors in the brain .	[97]
97	Somatropin	Somatropin belongs to the category of human growth hormones (HGH).	Somatropin is used to treat growth hormone deficiency in children and adults.	Somatropin targets the growth hormone receptor.	[98]
98	Dantrolene	Dantrolene belongs to the category of muscle relaxants.	Dantrolene can cause hepatotoxicity , which is liver damage	Dantrolene targets the sarcoplasmic reticulum in muscle cells to inhibit calcium release.	[99]
99	Fexofenadine	Fexofenadine belongs to the category of antihistamines medications used to treat allergies	Fexofenadine can cause drowsiness and dry mouth as common side effects.	Fexofenadine targets histamine H1 receptors to relieve allergy symptoms.	[100]
100	Vardenadil	Phosphodiesterase type 5 inhibitors	Vardenadil is a medication used to treat erectile dysfunction , not a disease or disorder itself.	Vardenadil primarily targets the phosphodiesterase type 5 (PDE5) enzyme to treat erectile dysfunction.	[101]

4. Future prospects

Intranasal drug delivery is an increasingly recognized method for administering medications, offering several advantages over traditional routes such as oral ingestion or injection. This method entails administering medications through the nasal mucosa, which permits their quick absorption into the bloodstream and their direct targeting of the CNS through the olfactory and trigeminal nerve pathways. In most cases, this leads to a more rapid

commencement of action, fewer systemic adverse effects, and higher rates of patient compliance. Research into the effectiveness of intranasal drug delivery has been conducted in a number of different therapeutic domains. For example, in the treatment of neurological disorders such as migraine, intranasal formulations of sumatriptan have been shown to provide rapid relief due to their ability to bypass the blood-brain barrier and reach the CNS more quickly than oral formulations. Similarly, intranasal delivery of insulin has been explored as a non-invasive

alternative for managing diabetes, with promising results in terms of glucose control and patient satisfaction. Furthermore, intranasal drug delivery has been utilized for vaccination purposes, offering potential advantages such as needle-free administration, improved immune response, and ease of mass vaccination campaigns. Intranasal vaccinations are an important part of public health initiatives since studies have shown that they are effective against respiratory illnesses including influenza and COVID-19. Intranasal drug delivery has several benefits, but there are also some problems that must be solved. These include variability in nasal anatomy and physiology among individuals, mucociliary clearance mechanisms that can limit drug absorption, and the need for optimized formulations to ensure adequate bioavailability. Additionally, the development of appropriate delivery devices is crucial for ensuring accurate dosing and patient comfort [102].

5. Conclusions

As an innovative platform, nasal medication delivery shows promise as an alternative to injectable administration. The introduction of other medications with nasal formulations for systemic treatment is possible soon. Many things go into the process of developing a medication with a drug delivery mechanism. Also anticipated for marketing are innovative nasal medicines for the treatment of long-term health conditions like diabetes, osteoporosis, and infertility. Nasal product development has several obstacles, one of the most significant being the bioavailability of nasal medicinal products. In contrast, a huge amount of money is investigated by pharmaceutical companies in the development of nasal products, because of growing demand of nasal drug products in global pharmaceutical market. So, for the avoidance of sideeffect and improve effectiveness of nasal products we should pay attention to basic research in nasal drug delivery.

Conflict of Interest

Author(s) declared no conflict of interest.

Ethical Compliance Standard

NA.

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